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An Empirical Study on Consumer Behaviour towards Online Shopping of Women Apparels in Kolhapur District

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Abstract

The internet revolution has redefined every business sector across the world especially online shopping and online shopping behavior of the people. The increased penetration of internet has fuelled the online retailing across the world and specifically in the emerging markets of developing countries like India. The Indian retailing market is evolving their business models into e-retailing models. The Indian industry of online retailing has crossed 20.5 Billion USD in the year 2017, and in 2018, it has crossed 25 billion USD and in 2021, there is expectation that it will increase up to 62 Billion USD. The Indian companies are facing challenges in identifying that what is driving the concept of theonline shopping.

Aim: This study is focused on behavior of customer on online shopping of women apparels, the various factors will be identifies that motivate the female shoppers to buy women apparels through online mode.

Method: This study is descriptive and exploratory research as the primary data is collected through self- structured questionnaire and analyzed that made to identify the customer behavior towards online shopping of women apparels. The structured questionnaire included Five Point Likert scale questions ranging from strongly agree to disagree. The respondents selected for this study are from Different taluk of Kolhapur like Chandgad, Bhudargad, Gadhinglaj, Ajara, Radhanagari, Shirol, shahuwadi, Hatkanangal etc. Due to times constraints, the convenience random sampling and cluster sampling method method had been used to collect the data and the total respondents selected for this study are 500. Anova test has been applied on collected data using SPSS Software to extract the various factors of customer's behavior towards online shopping of women apparels. **Conclusion:** The findings of this paper will provide deep insights regarding online retailing and consumer

behavior towards online shopping of Women Apparels to the small and big online International or National companies, Brands franchisee holder, retailers, Market strategy or policy makers.

Keywords: Indian Retailing Market, E-Retailing Models, Online Shopping, customer behavior.

1. Introduction

The internet revolution has redefined every business sector across the world especially online shopping and online shopping behavior of the people. The online shopping is regarded as the easiest solution for shopping in today's busy life scenario across the world. In the past decade, the customer shopping scenarios has witnessed the significant changes. The customers feel very convenient while shopping online; though customers are still buying from physical stores. The penetration of the internet and its affordability the internet users are increasing at higher pace. This has led retail businesses to move their business online in order to reach more and more customers through online mode. The online retailing is category of the electronic commerce that enables the small and big retailers to sale their products on the internet platforms such as websites and mobile applications. The customers have wide variety of options to choose from online websites and every product is available over the internet from needle to airplanes.

In India, there are various online shopping websites are operational; among them the bigger ones are Amazon, Flipkart, Myntra, Homeshop18, Snapdeal and Jabong. They offer wide variety of products right from Accessorise, Clothing, Electronics, Home Decor, Home furnishing, Gardening, Essentials and Medicines etc.

2. Review of literature

Singh (2014) studied the consumer's buying behavior towards online shopping by taking case study of the particular shopping website that is Flikart.com covering Lucknow City only. He stated that business opportunities for E-retailers are very bright in India; the E-retailers provide the consumers many benefits of the online shopping such as saving of

money and time, the flexibility of payments, budget, best prices and complete excellent experience of hassle free shopping.

Kanchan et.al (2015) conducted research study on online purchase behavior of customer in India and stated that online shopping has gained popularity in younger age groups with higher income and mostly they are educated. The security issues are main factor that cause shoppers to hesitate from buying the products online. The E-retailers should focus on making their platforms more secure and build trustworthy relationships with their customers.

Kothari and Maindargi (2016) conducted study on customer's attitude towards online shopping in India and its Impact taking reference of Solar city taking 100 respondents for the study. They stated that telecommunication advancement has increased internet users in India and also increased the online shopping customers. But the first choice of internet users is still traditional shopping from shops. The extensive publicity and promotion is required for boosting the online shopping. Most of the online shoppers considered the shipping charges are on high side that is being charged by the online retailing websites. They suggested the e- retailers that they should reduce their shipping charges; they should clearly make customers understand about return and refund policies; companies should provide after sales service to customers in order to increase their satisfaction and focus on increase loyalty among their customers.

Rao, M. B., Hymavathi, C. L., & Rao, M. M. (2018) conducted research study on the factors that affects the female consumer's online buying behavior and stated that the online retailing is very much different concept as compared with retail shopping; the factors that trigger the shoppers to shop online were identified in the research study. The identified factors were ease of use and convenience, time effectiveness, feedback, outbound logistics, and time effectives, these factors are main factors that influence the female buying behavior whole shopping online and the online retailers should focus on these factors in order to increase the satisfaction of the customers.

Dwivedi, C. K., & Mathur, D. G. (2019b) conducted a study on the consumer behavior towards online apparel purchase taking up the respondents from Indore city in

India. This research study aimed for identification of the relation between various factors which influences the consumer behavior while purchasing the apparels online. The total sample size for this study was 300 from the city of Indore in India and judgmental sampling was used. The findings of this research study suggests that there are factors that influence the behavior of the consumers while purchasing apparels online such as buying budget, security issues, privacy of their payment methods, the outlook and interface of the websites.

3. Research Methodology

This study is Descriptive and Exploratory research as the primary data is collected through self- structured questionnaire and analyzed that made to identify the behavior of customers towards online shopping of women apparels. The structured questionnaire included Five Point Likert scale questions ranging from strongly agree to disagree. Anova test has been applied on collected data using SPSS Software to extract the various factors of customer's behavior towards online shopping of women apparels.

Demographic characteristics were assessed in terms of age; monthly disposable income; employment; and Internet usage. Finally, willingness to provide credit card information online (if the price, brand quality, and retailer's reputation was acceptable) was measured on five point scales (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree).

4. Objectives of Study

To assess information consumers use while formulating perception of women apparel's product image, comfort, fabric characteristics, and fitting aspects.

5. Limitations

- 1) The total respondents selected for this study are from kolhapur District only.
- 2) All respondents are Female from all Age group as this study is related to womenapparels.
- 3) This study is based on educated Females only.
- 4) Due to pandemic situation, the questionnaire is administrated through online mode i.e. Google forms via Whatsapp, Facebook ,Sms, Instagram, e-mail id etc.

- 5) It is difficult to find results from respondent who take their own decisions or influenced with other factors like friends & relatives.

6. Universe of the study

The total respondents selected for this study are from Taluk of Kolhapur District like Chandgad, Bhudargad, Gadhinglaj, Ajara, Radhanagari, Shirol, Shahuwadi, Hatkanangal etc.

7. Sampling design

Simple random sampling method was adopted and total female respondents selected for this study are 500 from the Kolhapur District. To have a representative sample, respondents were chosen from different age groups.

8. Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant influence of reliability on buying behaviour of female consumer towards Online Shopping of Women Apparels.

H₁: There is a significant influence of reliability on buying behaviour of female consumer towards Online Shopping of Women Apparels.

9. Data analysis

To find the result of the Alternative hypothesis that is “There is no significant influence of reliability on buying behaviour of female consumer towards Online Shopping of Women Apparels” Anova test has been applied on collected data using SPSS Software to extract the various factors of customer’s behavior towards online shopping of women apparels.

Results of multivariate and univariate analysis showing differences between online purchasers and non purchasers of women apparel.

Variable	Group Mean		F – value	η^2	F - test
	Apparel purchases	Apparel non-purchases			
Demographics					16.52****
Age	35.69	35.58	11.662****	0.020	
Family Income	6.61	5.88	7.56****	0.016	
Qualification	3.76	3.74	4.69**	0.007	
Attitude towards online shopping					6.45****
Benefit	0.299	-0.004	21.22****	0.029	
Ease of use	0.135	-0.003	11.54****	0.021	
Enhances status	0.055	-0.020	3.74	0.005	
Safety	0.217	-0.034	11.51**	0.021	
Willing to provide information online					3.54****
Right price	3.11	3.03	1.010	0.002	
High quality	3.01	2.77	1.210		
Reputable retailer	3.72	3.68	7.979****	0.019	
Note: ****p<0.001; **p<0.01					

The results regarding female respondent’s willingness to provide financial and personal information online indicated that the purchasers and non- purchasers were significantly different with respect to their level of agreement to provide information online. In

general, female respondent's willingness to provide information if the retailer is trustworthy is significant at the level $p < 0.001$.

Reliability is the important factor that affects online buying and most of the female consumers are concerned about on-time delivery of their products. The result of the study shows that there is a significant association between reliability and online shopping. It is significant at 0.01 levels. Accordingly, the hypothesis could not be rejected. In addition, the direction of the associations is positive in which it indicates that the higher the reliability of the web site of e-retailers, the higher will be online buying. As such, there is a need for the e-retailers to ensure all aspects the reliability especially in term of product delivery should be guaranteed. This will enhance the acceptability of female consumers to participate more in an online buying experience.

10. Result-

Null hypothesis is rejected that is "There is no significant influence of reliability on buying behaviour of female consumer towards Online Shopping of Women Apparels." and Alternative hypothesis is accepted that is "There is significant influence of reliability on buying behaviour of female consumer towards Online Shopping of Women Apparels."

11. Conclusion

The female customers that are aware about the online shopping websites and their use are effective buyers of women apparels rather than unaware females about the online shopping website. The awareness plays an important role in influencing the buying behavior of female customers towards the online shopping of women apparels. The more awareness among the customer, the more they tend to buy women apparels online. The availability of the multiple brands and multiple varieties of apparels on the online shopping websites allures the women customers to buy the apparels online. The finding shows that in product attributes that are provided on online shopping websites are have significant influence on the buying behavior of the customers towards online shopping of women apparels. The safety and security while transacting on e-retailers websites that includes payments, delivery, product quality, refund and return policies are very much significant for the respondents while taking decision to buy women apparels online. The respondents

hesitate to buy from online retailers of women apparels those do not disclose their refund/return, payment and delivery policies. This factor highly influences the buying behavior of customers towards the online purchasing of women apparels. Due to consumers' concern with regard to transaction security and privacy in E-transmission, retailers are now more involved in improving e-transmission security and broader protection policies by providing customized strategies including return policies, interactivity and personalization on Web sites. Online retailers should also look into the possibility of running call centers which could ensure that the customer get a chance to formally interact with the other party before the actual purchase.

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